

Advanced integration of polymer microlens arrays with GaN microLEDs

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Advanced material processing and device fabrication technologies have offered the feasibility not only to create micron-scale light-emitting diodes (microLEDs) with a wide range of accessible wavelengths and low power consumption, but also to integrate them into microsystems as illumination sources for various applications beyond general solid-state lighting. Current ongoing development is focusing on the enhancement of internal quantum efficiencies and methods for improving light extraction efficiency either by modifying the device architecture or integrating other optical elements. However, integrating optical elements is a particular challenge as the dimensions of microLEDs scale down.

In this work, a reproducible processing method to fabricate and directly connect polymer-based microlens arrays on top of microLEDs has been developed and will be described here. Prior to device integration, the InGaN/GaN LED structures were prepared by metalorganic vapour phase epitaxy (MOVPE). The employed technique to realize the microlenses is based on thermal reflow, in which microstructured photoresist structures are created and subsequently transferred onto the desired surfaces (e.g., large-area LED and microLED arrays). Although the thermal softening and rounding effects of such polymers are not desired in some microtechnology processing steps (e.g., metallization), these have been employed for fabricating spin-on-glass-based microlens arrays [1]. However, the structures were only able to be produced on planar large area LEDs due to technology limitation. Therefore, when it comes to the micro-/nanostructured LED surfaces, a more sophisticated transfer methodology is required to overcome that issue. In this case, soft polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) stamps can be utilized for molding and further embossing the liquid polymer onto the structured microLED surfaces. Moreover, precise positioning of microlens arrays on GaN microLED arrays was demonstrated for an element size down to 10 μm . An optical characterization method based on 3D light beam profile scanning was developed allowing acquisition and analysis of the emission patterns of the integrated devices, in which the obtained results will be presented.

References

[1] Chi-Min Liu, Guo-Dung J Su, "Enhanced light extraction from UV LEDs using spin-on glass microlenses," J. Micromech. Microeng. 26 (2016).

Supplementary information

Figure 1 Array of 50 μm SU-8 microlenses integrated on a GaN LED surface.

Figure 2 Method for optical characterization of an array of SU-8 microlenses ($\varnothing = 50 \mu\text{m}$): microscopy images of the microlens array at three focusing positions, where z defines displacement of the objective focus from the glass substrate (top), statistical representation of the focal spot radii over the array (bottom left), and reconstructed light beam shape averaged over the array (bottom right).

Abstract

GaN microLEDs can be used as powerful integrated light sources in microsystems for various applications (e.g., microscopy, optogenetics, environmental sensors, and light data communication). However, the Lambertian angular intensity characteristic of the microLEDs causes the emission losses and spatial illumination resolution downgrade. This influence can be reduced by introducing high-precision microoptical elements to collimate the light beam emitted by the microLEDs. However, as the structure surface area are small and non-planar, direct integration of the microlenses onto microLEDs cannot be done with conventional fabrication methods. Thus, a device integration technique based on polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) structure transfer is proposed to guarantee precise positioning of polymer microlenses on top of microstructured LED surfaces. Moreover, owing to their superior properties (i.e., strong adhesion to GaN surface, high mechanical and chemical stability, and high transparency at UV-blue wavelengths), the realized SU-8 microlens arrays can be suitably combined with GaN microLEDs as versatile optical devices.

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